

Automated image analysis of ultrafast synchrotron CT scans to experimentally characterize the fibre break development during in-situ tensile tests

Christian Breite^{1*}, Erich Schöberl², Mark N. Mavrogordato²,
Larissa Gorbatikh¹, Stepan V. Lomov¹ and Yentl Swolfs¹

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¹ Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

² Engineering Materials, Faculty of Engineering and Physical Sciences,
University of Southampton, Southampton, United Kingdom

*Corresponding author (christian.breite@kuleuven.be)

3D microstructure of CFRP under load via in-situ SRCT

Specimen

Notch inside field of view

Fibre breaks

3D image analysis of each individual scan

Fibres

Fibre breaks

Broken fibres

Examples for generated modelling input data

Local fibre volume ratio

Orientation distribution

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